

ProQuest : A FULL- TEXT DATABASE

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ProQuest is a company that provides access to numerous databases, which are widely used for academic research and various other purposes. Apart from individual database search, many of these databases operate on a unified ProQuest platform, which provides consistent search functionalities and viewing options. Search techniques of the unified ProQuest platform has been discussed here.

➤ **Basic Search:**

● **Source Type Selection:**

We can search across all **ProQuest** platform databases (depending on our library subscription) with the Basic Search. We can search **all** source types or choose to limit our search by a particular source type such as Scholarly Journals, Videos & Audio, Dissertations & Theses, Books and others that are available through the **‘All Source Types’ option**.

<https://www.proquest.com/>

Source type depends on individual databases but here we are concerned with the unified ProQuest platform.

Basic Search tips:

ProQuest
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Jadavpur University

You are searching 8 databases

Basic Search | Advanced Search | Publications | Browse | Change Databases

All | Scholarly journals | Books | Videos & Audio | Dissertations & Theses | All source types +

Search tips

Search tips: Step 1 of 4

If you enter more than one word (e.g. artificial intelligence) the search will find records containing all of your search terms.

Use quotation marks ("artificial intelligence") to search for exact phrases.

Entering multiple search terms or using phrase searching can help you get more relevant results.

Next

ProQuest

You are searching 8 databases

Basic Search | Advanced Search | Publications | Browse

Step 2 of 4

The search engine will automatically look for variant forms of your search terms. These include plurals, different forms of adjectives, and alternative American and British spellings.

Searching for **labor** will also find **labour**.
Searching for **tall** will also find **taller** and **tallest**.
Searching for **mouse** will also find **mice**.
Searching for **elephants** will also find **elephant**.

To search only for the exact term that you type, use quotation marks.

Searching for "mouse" will ONLY find mouse.

Back | Next

ProQuest

You are searching 8 databases

Basic Search | Advanced Search | Publications | Browse

All | Scholarly Jo

Step 3 of 4

There are special characters and operators that can be used to further control your search.

The asterisk (*) is a truncation character, used to replace one or more characters at the right or in the middle of a word.

For example, **econom*** will find economy, economic or economist.

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Search tips

Step 4 of 4

You can use the **NEAR** operator to find documents where the search terms are separated by up to a certain number of words of each other (either before or after)

For example, **franklin NEAR roosevelt** will find both Franklin D. Roosevelt and Franklin Delano Roosevelt, as well as Franklin Roosevelt.

By default it will find records with the words separated by up to 4 words. To change this you can use the **r** character and a number, for example **diversity NEAR3 training** will find records where the words appear with a maximum of 3 intervening words.

For more details on special characters and operators, please see our [LibGuide](#)

Back | Close

System search defaults:

- 2 or more words separated by space are searched with an implicit AND. In the example below, we can see that same number of results have been shown, though the sequence of the results has changed.

The screenshot shows the ProQuest search interface. The search bar contains the text "Media Literacy". Below the search bar, it indicates "810,814 results". On the left side, there are filters for "Sorted by" (set to Relevance), "Limit to" (Full text, Peer reviewed), and "Source type" (Scholarly Journals, Books, Dissertations & Theses, Newspapers, Magazines). The main results area shows two entries, both identified as "Dissertation or Thesis". The first entry is "The implementation of media literacy: An analysis of the media literacy curricula of Ontario, Canada; New South Wales, Australia, and England" by Taylor, Teresa Renee. The second entry is "Exploring the complexities of personal ideologies, media literacy pedagogy and media literacy practice" by Damico, Amy M. On the right side, there is a section titled "Books that match your search" with two book covers visible.

Boolean search:

Fig. 9.1 Boolean searches

AND Search →

This screenshot shows a ProQuest search interface for the query "information AND management". The search bar at the top contains the text "information AND management". The results section displays "5,273,595 results". Two search results are visible:

- Result 1:** "Building GIS for Sustainable Conservation and Management of Riverine Heritage Landscapes: MERSGIS for Meander (Meander) River Delta, Turkey". Authors: Derman, Hilmiye; Nigiz Akbulut, Ayşe Güllü; Yemcihan Şahin, Seray. *The International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, Göttingen, Vol. XLIIB/14, 2024. Cooperative GIMM (2024): 1113-1126. Abstracts: Full text - PDF view.
- Result 2:** "An Evaluation of the Environmental Health Information System in Municipalities in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa... and the Design of a Digital Model". Authors: Mkhomo, Siphosiso; Swembele, University of Johannesburg (South Africa) ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, 2024. 3220766. Abstracts: Full text - PDF view.

The interface includes a sidebar with filters for "Sorted by" (Relevance), "Limit to" (Full text, Peer reviewed), and "Source type" (Scholarly Journals, Books, Dissertations & Theses, Newspapers, Magazines).

This screenshot shows a ProQuest search interface for the query "knockout AND mice". The search bar at the top contains the text "knockout AND mice". The results section displays "810,814 results" and "349,851 results" (likely a sub-filtered view). One search result is visible:

- Result 1:** "Scavenger receptor class B type I knockout mice develop extensive diet-induced coronary artery atherosclerosis in an age-dependent manner". Authors: Lee, Samuel K; Kong, Ting; Qian, Alexander S; Jeong Ah Lee, B.; Sumayyah H. Sulekchand; et al. *PLoS One*; San Francisco Vol. 20, Iss. 5, (May 2025): e0318118. Abstract: Full text - PDF view.

The interface includes a sidebar with filters for "Sorted by" (Relevance), "Limit to" (Full text, Peer reviewed), and "Source type" (Scholarly Journals, Books, Dissertations & Theses).

OR Search →

OR finds records containing any one of the search terms or both the search terms.

NOT Search →

NOT finds records that do not contain the term following it.

Truncation and Wildcard Search →

- The truncation character asterisk (*) is used to replace one or more characters. The truncation character can be used at the end (right-hand truncation), or in the middle of a word. Truncation and Wildcard work in a similar way, **cat?** will return matches on both **cat** and **cats**. Similarly, **cat??** will return documents with matches on **cat**, **cats**, and **catch**—0, 1, or 2 characters respectively.

Left-truncation and wildcard at left are not allowed.

Maximum 5 characters will be retrieved in this way. A number can be entered next to the asterisk to define up to how many characters will be retrieved. The max number supported is 20. This way the default limit of max 5 characters can be overcome.

ProQuest Access provided by Jadavpur University

Search: bom[*12]

3,721,921 results

Modify search Recent searches Save search/alert

Show results outside my library's subscription.

Sorted by: Relevance

Limit to: Full text Peer reviewed

Source type: Scholarly Journals Books Audio & Video Works Dissertations & Theses Newspapers

Select 1-20

Quick look

Working Paper

STANet: A Novel Spatio-Temporal Aggregation Network for Depression Classification with Small and Unbalanced FMM Data
Zhang, Wei; Zeng, Wenming; Chen, Hongxiu; Liu, Jie; Wu, Hongjie; et al. *arXiv.org: ePrints*, Nov 23, 2024.
...self-report questionnaires and clinical assessment, lacking objective **biomarkers**...

Working Paper

Simplifying Causal Mediation Analysis for Time-to-Event Outcomes using Pseudo Values
Ocampo, Alex; Gladon, Dennis; Håberg, Dieter A; Magnusson, Baldur; Lange, Thorir; et al. *arXiv.org: ePrints*, Nov 26, 2024.
...**biomarker** lies on the causal path between treatment and time-to-event, which... **biomarker** as a surrogate outcome. Our approach greatly simplifies mediation...

Books that match your search

Biometric and Biomedical Statistics: Design, Synthesis, & Taylor & Francis Group, Dec 23, 2023.

Artificial Intelligence for **Biometric** Based Worker Profit Taylor & Francis Group, Dec 16, 2023.

For example, **Cata[*3]** and **Cata???**

Search: cata[*3]

1,336,505 results

Modify search

Show results outside my library's subscription.

Sorted by: Relevance

Limit to: Full text Peer reviewed

Source type: Scholarly Journals Books Audio & Video Works Dissertations & Theses Newspapers

Select 101-120

Quick look

Working Paper

Two-loop QCD corrections for the process Pseudo-scalar Higgs $\rightarrow 3$ photons
Bakker, Pieter; Chark, Prasanna K; Ravindran, V. *arXiv.org: ePrints*, Nov 10, 2024.
...by **Cata**. For both the amplitudes namely $A \rightarrow 3$ and...

Working Paper

Eccentricities of Close Stellar Binaries
Wu, Hongjie; Hadden, Sara; Gendreau, James; El Radry, Kamran; Motzner, Christopher D. *arXiv.org: ePrints*, Nov 15, 2024.
...and **Cata** to reveal that, binaries towards of a few AU exhibit a simple...

Working Paper

Metabonomics biomarkers of health: a longitudinal study of aging female and male mice

Another type of nested search

Limit Search →

- **Range Search:**

The field code **YR** is used with a **hyphen (-)** between the years to indicate a specific time range of date of publication.

Example: YR(2015-2018)

The **less than** or **greater than** symbols (**<** or **>**) are used to indicate before/after the publication date.

When sorted by relevance, the range search doesn't work properly and gives unwanted result. For example, the above search also retrieves documents published in 2016.

The screenshot shows the ProQuest search interface. At the top, the search criteria are "INTEROPERABILITY AND CROSSWALK AND YR (>2023)". The results are sorted by "Relevance" and show 144 results. The first result is "Application of Clinical Bioinformatics" by Dordrecht, NL, Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, Apr 13, 2016. The second result is "International Encyclopedia of Education" by Chantilly, GB, Chantilly: Elsevier Science & Technology, Nov 1, 2022. The search criteria and the date of the first result are highlighted with red boxes.

Phrase Search →

In this type of search, only specific keyword related articles. Show Another type of variant searching is lemmatization i.e. different grammatical forms, singular, plural, superlative degree etc.

- quotation marks " " is put to search for exact phrases.
- **Variants searching**- putting terms within the quotation marks temporarily deactivates the Variants searching. To search an exact phrase and keep the Variants searching

active, quotation and curly brackets are used together. An example of spelling variant search is given below.

Only 539 results with 'organisation'. The spelling 'organization' is not retrieved.

When {} and "" are applied together, the increase in the number of results can be seen.

Field Search →

Here “su” mean **subject**, so only where **public library** is subject, by this search only this 2 results is retrieved.

Similarly there are other numerous field codes, which are not directly provided in the libguide but mentioned in an additional search guide.

An example with **TI** (for title):

Nested Search →

The screenshot shows a ProQuest search interface with the query "(classification OR data) AND (information OR catalog/ing)". The results page displays 9,307,874 results. The search results are sorted by Relevance. The first result is "Policies and Practices: How to Improve Data Classification in Higher Education" by Johnson, Lisa, Johnson, Heather, published in *EDUCAUSE Review (Online): Boulder* (Feb 4, 2025). The second result is "Summer Global LST Variability Across Local Climate Zones Using ECOSTRESS Data in Lecce and Milan" by Papapanagiotou, Georgia, Espinoza, Antonio, Maccohen-Ricardo, published in *Atmosphere: Basel* Vol. 16, Iss. 4, (2025): 377. The interface includes filters for source type (Scholarly Journals, Books, Audio & Video Works, Dissertations & Theses, Newspapers) and options to limit results to full text or peer-reviewed content.

- **Proximity Operators:**

NEAR/4 or **N/4** is used to retrieve documents where there are up to 4 intervening words between the search terms.

The screenshot shows a ProQuest search interface with the query "interoperability NEAR/4 digital library". The results page displays 4,370 results. The search results are sorted by Relevance. The first result is "Interoperability as a Catalyst for Digital Health and Therapeutics: A Scoping Review of Emerging Technologies and Standards (2015-2025)" by Adegoke Kola, Adegoke Abimbola, Dawodu Deborah, Adekoya Akorede, Ayoola, Bayowa, et al., published in *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health; Basel* Vol. 22, Iss. 10, (2025): 1535. The abstract snippet reads: "... 2.1.5. Interoperability in Digital Therapeutics and Chronic Care ... review aims to map the breadth of the literature (2015-2025) on digital health ... learning are being integrated to support digital health interoperability ...". The interface includes filters for source type (Scholarly Journals, Books) and options to limit results to full text or peer-reviewed content.